

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for Generation of the transition list of fragments of labeled standards used for targeted analysis on GC-MS

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Summary

This SOP will focus on the creation of the transition list of fragments of labeled standards used for targeted analysis.

Software needed: MS-LIMA, NIST library (online or offline version), MS-DIAL, Skyline

Data needed: acquired full-scan data of the standards you need for the library, for easier distinguishing of the specific analytes, single analytes, may be measured beside the pooled standard sample

A. Uploading the NIST theoretical .msp library into MS-LIMA for visualization of the fragmentation pattern

1. Open MS-LIMA ver. 1.54
2. Find your .msp library of the standards created of GC-MS spectra from NIST

NOTE: .msp library must be created by merging linear MSP format GC Spectra. How to generate .msp library is in detail described in SOPs for: "[Extracting GC MS spectra from NIST Mass Spectral Library](#)"; "[Conversion MSP format to linear MSP format via Lib2NIST Library Conversion Tool](#)" and "[Merging multiple individual MSPs files into one single MSP file via TXTcollector software](#)" in this order.

3. Open MS-LIMA → File → Import → Import → Select your .msp library → Open
4. The multitable window with names of the metabolites and spectra will open (Figure 1)
5. From the list of metabolites in the bottom right corner, select your desired metabolite and click on it (Figure 1: 1).
6. Drag the mouse cursor to the top left corner of one of the peaks (Figure 1: 2). The fragment to which this peak corresponds will be shown in the box (Figure 1: 3).

Figure 1 - Orientation in MS-LIMA software and visualisation of the fragmentation

B. Searching for the labelled metabolite structure online

1. Search for the metabolite with corresponding labelling online (on the vendor websites)
2. Find the structure of the labelled metabolite you are using (Figure 2)

Figure 2 - Structure of the labelled metabolite

NOTE: Sigma Aldrich is here shown just because the labelled standard was ordered from this vendor, thus the structure will look like this. There is always possibility to draw structure in software designed for structure drawing like ChemDraw or ChemSketch and let the software calculate the molecular weight of the labelled standard.

NOTE: Different vendors may offer differently labelled standards of the same type. Because of this is important to know where you ordered the standard from so you have the correct structure.

C. Merging structural information (B) with the fragmentation pattern of the molecule (A)

1. Check the structure of the spectra (Figure 1), see the selected fragment and align it with the structure of the labelled structure (Figure 2) to figure out how many labels will be on this fragment (Figure 3)

Figure 3 - Merging structural information with fragmentation pattern of the molecule

2. Calculate the expected m/z of this labelled fragment (Equation 1); see the note below.

$$m/z_{\text{labeled}} = m/z_{\text{native}} + X \times (Mw_{\text{Deut}} - Mw_{\text{Hydr}})$$

where X is number of labels on the fragment; $Mw_{\text{Deut}} = 2,0141$ and $Mw_{\text{Hydr}} = 1,008$, from which we can assume the Δ will be 1,006 \rightarrow this value could be used further.

Equation 1 - Calculation of the m/z of labelled fragment

NOTE: Example of calculation on the hexanoic acid-d11 – we can see that the fragment with m/z 60,032 will have 2 deuterium on its structure. From this information we can calculate the m/z of the labelled fragment being 60,032 + 2x1,006 (here we are adding only the difference of 1,006 to the normal hydrogen that would normally be on that bond). The final weight of this fragment then would be 62,0442 m/z. This is the value we will be using further in searching for the labelled standards in the samples.

3. Repeat this process for all the main fragments of all the observed metabolites to obtain list of the m/z for labelled molecules.
4. Create **the preliminary transition list in Excel table** and write down all the calculated masses of fragments with corresponding analyte.

NOTE: Optimal is to create this list directly according to the format that is required for Skyline software (Figure 4) containing: Compound Group Name, Compound Name, Precursor m/z, Product m/z (in case of single MS analysis will be the same as the Precursor m/z). It is also convenient to have in this table retention times for the corresponding analytes.

Compound Group	Compound Name	Precursor	Product m/z	precursor	product ch	Fragmentc	Cell	Accel	Polarity	Retention time
SCFA deu	acetic acid (2)	46.02	46.02	1	1	130		4	Positive	5.7
SCFA deu	acetic acid (2)	64.04	64.04	1	1	130		4	Positive	5.7
SCFA deu	propionic acid (3)	45.04	45.04	1	1	130		4	Positive	6.5
SCFA deu	propionic acid (3)	60.08	60.08	1	1	130		4	Positive	6.5
SCFA deu	isobutyric acid (i4)	49.08	49.08	1	1	130		4	Positive	6.7

Figure 4 - Transition list in Excel in the format required by Skyline software

D. Checking the presence of the labelled standards in the spectra

1. Open MS-DIAL ver. 4.9
2. Import data of your measured standards exported from Chromeleon in .raw file

NOTE: How to operate MS-DIAL for identification and deconvolution of the spectra is shown in “[SOP for High-Resolution EI+ mass spectral libraries \(HR-\[EI+\]-MS\) building via GC-Orbitrap MS](#)”.

3. Select the metabolite you have the list of m/z for labelled standards already prepared
4. View → Display extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) (Figure 5)

Figure 5 - Displaying of the Extracted ion chromatogram (EIC)

5. Fill the data of m/z and Mass tolerance (usually 0,5 m/z) into the emerged EIC table (Figure 6) → Display

Figure 7 - EIC table

6. In the EIC figure (Figure 7), find the peak with corresponding ions and zoom in to see which exact RT it appears at.

Figure 6 - EIC spectra, RT selection

NOTE: Which of the peaks is the desired analyte can be assumed by the retention index (RI) comparison between the analyte and alkanes measured under the same conditions. The RI of the analyte could be found in NIST library – both online (<https://webbook.nist.gov/>) and desktop offline application (NIST MS Search 2.3). Structure of the online and how to find the RI there is shown in Figure 8, structure of the offline desktop application is then shown in Figure 10.

NOTE: In online NIST RI can be found in the Gas Chromatography tab (Figure 8: 1). Select corresponding column type, temperature program and RI calculation (Figure 8: 2), find the length

of the column and specific type of column same or at least the most similar to yours and that shown RI (Figure 8: 4) is the one that should correspond to your analyte.

- Based on the RT obtained by combination of RI from online NIST (Figure 8) and the EIC from MS Dial (Figure 7), select specific peak in the Peak Spot viewer in MS-DIAL main screen (Figure 9).

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NIST Chemistry WebBook, SRD 69

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Hexanoic acid

- Formula: C₆H₁₂O₂
- Molecular weight: 116.1583
- IUPAC Standard InChI: InChI=1S/C6H12O2/c1-2-3-4-5-6(7)8/h2-5H2,1H3,(H,7,8) InChI v 1.06
- IUPAC Standard InChIKey: FUZZVXG5FPDMH-UHFFFAOYSA-N
- CAS Registry Number: 142-62-1
- Chemical structure: CCCCCCCC(=O)O

This structure is also available as a 2d Mol file or as a computed 3d SD file. The 3d structure may be viewed using Java or Javascript.

- Other names: Caproic acid; n-Caproic acid; n-Hexanoic acid; n-Hexoic acid; n acid; Hexacid 698; Kyselina kapronova; Pentanecarboxylic acid; NSC 8266
- Permanent link for this species. Use this link for bookmarking this species for future visits.
- Information on this page:
 - Notes
 - Other data available:
 - Gas phase thermochemistry data
 - Condensed phase thermochemistry data
 - Phase change data
 - Reaction thermochemistry data
 - Henry's Law data
 - Gas phase ion energetics data
 - IR Spectrum
 - Mass spectrum (electron ionization)
 - Gas Chromatography

View large format table.

Column type	Active phase	I	Reference	Comment
Capillary	DB-Wax	1854	Botelho, Caldeira, et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.25 µm, He, 50. C @ 2. min, 3.5 K/min, 180. C @ 25. min
Capillary	Innowax	1863	Botelho, Caldeira, et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.25 µm, H2, 45. C @ 5. min, 3.5 K/min, 210. C @ 20. min
Capillary	DB-FFAP	1839	Jarunrattanasri, Theerakulkail, et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.5 µm, He, 35. C @ 5. min, 4. K/min, 225. C @ 30. min
Capillary	DB-FFAP	1839	Jarunrattanasri, Theerakulkail, et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.5 µm, He, 35. C @ 5. min, 4. K/min, 225. C @ 30. min
Capillary	FFAP	1824	Lozano P.R., Drake M., et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.25 µm, He, 35. C @ 5. min, 10. K/min, 225. C @ 25. min
Capillary	FFAP	1854	Lozano P.R., Misacle E.R., et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.25 µm, He, 35. C @ 5. min, 10. K/min, 225. C @ 25. min
Capillary	DB-Wax	1851	Pozo-Bayon M.A., Ruiz-Rodriguez A., et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.5 µm, He, 40. C @ 5. min, 4. K/min, 250. C @ 15. min
Capillary	DB-Wax	1866	Pozo-Bayon M.A., Ruiz-Rodriguez A., et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.5 µm, He, 40. C @ 5. min, 4. K/min, 250. C @ 15. min
Capillary	DB-Wax	1851	Pozo-Bayon M.A., Ruiz-Rodriguez A., et al., 2007	30. m/0.25 mm/0.5 µm, He, 40. C @ 5. min, 4. K/min, 250. C @ 15. min
Capillary	HP-1	1811	Quijano, Linares, et al., 2007	60. m/0.25 mm/0.25 µm, He, 50. C @ 4. min, 4. K/min, 220. C @ 10. min

Figure 9 - Online NIST library and how to search RI of the analyte there

Figure 8 - Peak Spot viewer visualisation in MS-DIAL

E. Checking the correctness of the identity of your peak

Comparing the MS Spectra and RI of the theoretical NIST library and the measured result

1. Open NIST → type the name of compound → search for the compound
2. Compare the acquired spectra (Figure 9) with the NIST spectra (Figure 10 2a)
3. Compare the RI of the acquired spectra obtained via MS Dial (Figure 9) with the NIST RI (in online version Figure 8, in offline version Figure 10 2b)
 - a. Open NIST (preferably offline desktop version) → type the name of compound → search for the RI corresponding for the column we are using = this is the theoretical RI (Figure 10)
 - b. MS-DIAL → in the import, upload the text document with alkanes and their retention times from the column used for analysis of the analytes

NOTE: This step will allow the software to create RI for your analytes that will further show in the MS-DIAL software.

NOTE: How to use MS-DIAL is explained in the

4. Both spectra and RI must fit the potential compound to be correctly assigned

Figure 10 – NIST desktop application comparison of spectra and RIs

NOTE: In the spectra, there will be slight differences in the values of m/z since the theoretical MS spectrum is of native metabolite and the measured one is of the labelled metabolites. Here for checking of the correct masses, use the values of m/z calculated before in Equation 1. Comparison of the spectra is **important mainly for the abundance of specific m/z values**.

NOTE: This step could also be done using MS-LIMA, since the spectrum is already opened there and the .msp library is created from the spectra in NIST library. This step could be also done at the end when you have specific ions for analytes → then open MS-LIMA and this library, where the labelled versions will already be present, and the spectra will be precise. Then you can double check the preciseness and selectivity of the peak you selected.

NOTE: In the text document with RTs be aware about extra spaces and tabs – it will cause MS-DIAL to crash if it is not correctly written. Rather just overwrite the file, that you know worked before and do

not create the new one. For each method, new document must be created since the RTs will be different based on the GC temperature ramp and PTV temperature ramp.

F. Choosing specific ions for each analyte using MS-LIMA

1. Open MS-LIMA software
2. Import .msp library created from empirical measurements of both labelled and native standards (how to create library is in detail described in **SOP for High-Resolution EI+ mass spectral libraries (HR-[EI+]-MS) building via GC-Orbitrap MS**)
3. Viewer → Show Comparative mass spectra viewer
4. Select native analyte in one of the columns (here in the left one, under number 1) (Figure 11)
5. Select the same analyte but in labelled version in the second column (here in the right one, under number 2) (Figure 11)
6. See the comparison mass spectra where the upper spectra is the left column (here native analyte) and the lower spectra is the right column (here labelled analyte). (Figure 11)
7. Based on your RT window, select the ions that are specific for each analyte – the native and the labelled one, so they are not overlapped neither between those two analogous analytes and neither between their closest neighbours, see example in note.

NOTE: For example, if your analyte is native butyric acid with RT of 7.21 minutes and your RT window is set to 0.5 minutes, you should consider a range of 6.71 to 7.71 minutes. Avoid using the same ion multiple times within this range, as it may interfere with other analytes and your SIM analysis won't be as accurate.

G. Checking of the standards using Skyline

1. Open Skyline software
2. Import created Transition list of the new m/z (Figure 13)

1

Molecule and transition settings needs to be set here – that will be done based on your method and data you have.

2

Compound Group	Compound Name	Precursor m/z	Product m/z	precursor charge	product charge	Fragmentor
SCFA mix	acetic acid (2)	43.05	43.05	1	1	130
SCFA mix	acetic acid (2)	60.02	60.02	1	1	130
SCFA mix	acetic acid (2) -d4	46.05	46.05	1	1	130
SCFA mix	acetic acid (2) -d4	63.03	63.03	1	1	130
SCFA mix	butyric acid (4)	41.07	41.07	1	1	130
SCFA mix	butyric acid (4)	55.03	55.03	1	1	130
SCFA mix	butyric acid (4)	60.03	60.03	1	1	130
SCFA mix	butyric acid (4)	73.03	73.03	1	1	130
SCFA mix	butyric acid (4) -d7	58.03	58.03	1	1	130
SCFA mix	butyric acid (4) -d7	63	63	1	1	130
SCFA mix	butyric acid (4) -d7	95.09	95.09	1	1	130

3

4

Targets

- SCFA mix
 - acetic acid (2)
 - acetic acid (2) -d4
 - propionic acid (3)
 - 57.0700+
 - 74.0600[M16.99+] (heavy)
 - propionic acid (3) -d3
 - 60.0600+
 - 76.0700[M16.01+] (heavy)
 - isobutyric acid (4)
 - isobutyric acid (4) -d7
 - butyric acid (4)
 - butyric acid (4) -d7
 - isovaleric acid (5)
 - isovaleric acid (5) -d9
 - valeric acid (5)
 - valeric acid (5) -d9
 - hexanoic acid (6)
 - hexanoic acid (6) -d11
 - heptanoic acid (7)
 - heptanoic acid (7) -d13

Figure 12 - Skyline - Importing the created transition list

NOTE: The easiest way to import new Transition list into the Skyline is directly through the main page just after opening the software. Then easy Copy – Paste from your Excel sheet is enough to import the data. Select the names for the columns in use and then the Skyline will be created.

NOTE: The transition list to Skyline must stick to specific format in Excel / .csv (Figure 4). It could be directly imported, or it could be copy pasted into the template in Skyline.

3. Save your file with the transition list as template for later.
4. Import the results of your measured standards via File → Import → Results
5. Check the corresponding samples with the corresponding analyte, you should be able to see one specific peak.
6. If you see one peak in the correct RT, you can say these ions are specific to this analyte in this RT and you can consider this transition list done and correct.